

MODELS FOR INCREASING THE SYNERGISTIC EFFICIENCY OF SERVICES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The thesis studies the synergistic effectiveness of services in education, its essence, possibilities, and results. The thesis is aimed at the application of models, perspectives, and methods for increasing synergistic efficiency and improving the quality of education.*

Keywords: *synergistic, efficiency, licensing, commercial transfer, integral coefficients.*

A study of scientific sources on synergies showed that there is no acceptable methodology for assessing the synergistic effectiveness of internal and horizontal integration in improving the quality of educational services.

It is important to identify the main problems and factors that reduce the quality of education in Uzbekistan, analyze the most important indicators, and develop synergistic features for assessing indicators that characterize the educational process and quality based on state statistical data.

Development trends in the world's countries show that the level of development of different countries varies in accordance with the level of development of their education systems, in particular, the higher education system. Because while the development of the higher education system until the end of the 20th century took place with a certain delay (the period until the graduation of specialists admitted to the higher education system), in today's conditions of innovative development, this delay period is being minimized. The results of the study show that improving the quality of educational services is achieved by optimizing the educational process through scientifically based analysis and effective allocation of resources.

Therefore, using A.A. Garmider's methodological approach to assessing the synergistic effect, we propose the following formula for determining the integral coefficient summarizing the synergistic effect of improving the quality of educational services:

$$I_{se} = \sqrt[3]{I_k \cdot I_s \cdot I_q}$$

Here: I_{se} — generalizing integral coefficient of synergistic effect;

I_k, I_s, I_q – integral coefficients characterizing synergistic effects on the knowledge, skills, and proficiency levels of students (pupils). The integral coefficients of synergistic effects on knowledge, skills, and competencies are calculated similarly by taking the cube root of the three indicators.

The integral economic efficiency indicator, which characterizes the synergistic effects of educational services, is determined by the following formula:

$$I_{ee} = \frac{ee_1}{ee_2}$$

Here: I_{ee} - integral coefficient characterizing synergistic effects in the economic sphere, ee_1 – Economic efficiency indicator of educational services after the implementation of current synergistic measures, ee_2 – Economic efficiency indicator of educational services after the implementation of synergistic measures in the baseline period.

Determining the synergistic effectiveness of educational services using these formulas serves as the basis for developing future measures and activities. We used empirical modeling to assess the quality of educational services and measure synergistic effectiveness. A theoretical analysis of the process of assessing the synergistic effectiveness of improving the quality of educational services showed that currently its theory is in a paradigm state, that is, it is the level of theory accepted by most people to solve current research problems.

We used empirical modeling to assess the quality of educational services and measure synergistic effectiveness. A theoretical analysis of the process of assessing the synergistic effectiveness of improving the quality of educational services showed that currently its theory is in a paradigm state, that is, it is the level of theory accepted by most people to solve current research problems.

Synergistic effectiveness of educational services refers to increasing the overall effectiveness of education through the interaction of various components. Synergy is when individual components work together to produce a greater result than if they were working alone.

This process often involves the integration of various factors of the educational process, including teachers, students, infrastructure, technology, and curricula. This is aimed at improving the quality of education, adapting students to global requirements, and increasing the efficiency of the educational process. Innovative and continuous development of the education system is essential for training competitive, knowledgeable, and skilled personnel in the future.

In our opinion, it is advisable to use the following methods of synergy to ensure the quality and efficiency of educational services:

First, it is necessary to join forces. In this, the entities interested in the education of students - parents, students, teachers, educational institutions, employers, and the state - must join forces;

secondly, to have a systemic impact. In this, each individual and each team must have a systemic impact together. Criteria for synergistic assessment of the quality and effectiveness of training for educational institutions and employers.

The graph above shows the synergistic assessment criteria for the level of information and digitization, that is, the level of information and digitization:

the first criterion is the speed of adaptation to new environmental conditions;

the second criterion is the efficiency of using digital resources and tools;

the third criterion is the effectiveness of all participants in using the capabilities of digital platforms;

the fourth indicates the level of development of digital competence among participants, and the fifth indicates the size of the database.

So, in conclusion, it is worth saying that it is advisable to strengthen the prospects of educational services, their special role in education, their specific characteristics in the country and its regions, and the effect of synergy, and to implement a number of measures in our republic, including the development of forms of cooperation such as franchising, commercial triangulation, project financing, contract management, licensing, and commercial transfer, which are widespread in foreign countries.

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